

DEVELOPMENT OF BACTERIOCIN-BASED BIOPRESERVATIVE FOR EXTENDING SHELF LIFE OF MILK AND MILK PRODUCT

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Article Received on 22 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 14 March 2026,
Article Published on 01 April 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19330584>

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How To Cite This Article: Ms. Alfiya Momin*, Prof. (Dr.) Savanta Raut (2026). Development of Bacteriocin-Based Biopreservative for Extending Shelf Life of Milk and Milk Product. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(4), 555–582.

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ABSTRACT

Milk and traditional milk-based products are highly susceptible to microbial spoilage due to their rich nutrient composition and high moisture content. The demand for safe and natural preservation methods has increased interest in bacteriocins as potential biopreservatives. The present study aimed to develop and evaluate a bacteriocin-based preservation system for extending the shelf life of milk and a traditional milk product, barfi. Bacteriocin-producing strains including *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Bacillus clausii*, and *Bacillus coagulans* were screened for antimicrobial activity. Crude bacteriocins were extracted and partially purified using ethyl acetate. Among the tested strains, *L. rhamnosus* showed significant inhibitory activity against selected foodborne pathogens. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) analysis confirmed its effectiveness at relatively low concentrations. Protein estimation was carried out using the Folin–Lowry method.

Application studies in milk and barfi demonstrated that bacteriocin treatment effectively delayed microbial growth and reduced spoilage. Microbiological and physicochemical parameters such as total viable count, coliform count, pH, titratable acidity, and Methylene Blue Reduction Test (MBRT) indicated improved stability in treated samples compared to controls. Incorporation of bacteriocin into a bioactive coating also contributed to extended shelf life in barfi. The findings suggest that bacteriocin from *L. rhamnosus* has promising potential as a natural biopreservative for milk and milk-based products.

KEYWORDS: Bacteriocin, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, Biopreservation, Milk, Barfi, Shelf Life.

INTRODUCTION

Bovine milk is an important part of human nutrition worldwide and is often described as a "complete food" because it contains high-quality proteins such as casein and lactalbumins, essential fats, and easily absorbable minerals like calcium and phosphorus. In addition to being consumed directly, milk also serves as a major industrial raw material and is used in the production of nearly 8,000 to 10,000 different dairy products globally. However, the same rich nutrient composition that makes milk valuable for human health also makes it highly suitable for microbial growth. As a result, milk is very prone to spoilage. Globally, more than six billion people consume dairy products, yet almost 16% of total production is lost before reaching markets in low-income regions, leading to annual economic losses of more than US \$2–3 billion (Lau *et al.*, 2023; Fekata *et al.*, 2023).

To reduce these losses, the dairy industry has traditionally depended on heat treatment and the use of chemical preservatives. In certain laboratory and regional practices, chemicals such as potassium dichromate, sodium azide, and bronopol are used to extend shelf life, especially for testing and quality control purposes. However, these substances have important limitations, including environmental toxicity, health hazards for laboratory personnel, and possible interference with analytical results (Chalermisan *et al.*, 2004). Because of these concerns, consumers are increasingly demanding "clean-label" products that contain fewer synthetic additives. This shift has encouraged researchers to explore natural, safe, and effective alternatives, particularly in the form of biopreservatives.

The issue of preservation becomes even more challenging in traditional Indian milk-based sweets such as barfi. Barfi is prepared by heat-desiccating milk to form khoa, followed by the addition of sugar. This process produces a product that is rich in nutrients and has intermediate moisture content, conditions that favor microbial growth (Chawla *et al.*, 2015). Although the initial heating step reduces the microbial load, contamination can still occur during handling, shaping, packaging, and storage. Yeasts and molds are the main causes of spoilage in barfi, leading to off-flavors, discoloration, and undesirable texture changes. In addition, bacterial contaminants such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and coliforms may pose public health risks (Dhakane *et al.*, 2019). Due to these factors, the shelf life of conventional barfi stored at room temperature is usually limited to about 10–12 days.

Biological preservation, also known as biopreservation, has emerged as a promising alternative to synthetic preservatives. Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) have been widely used as starter cultures because they are classified as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) and are capable of producing several antimicrobial compounds, including organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, and diacetyl (Grujovic *et al.*, 2022). Recent studies have also shown that LAB isolated from non-conventional sources can inhibit important foodborne pathogens such as *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Darko *et al.*, 2025). In addition to LAB, species belonging to the genus *Bacillus*, particularly *B. subtilis*, have gained attention as producers of antimicrobial peptides. Unlike many LAB, *Bacillus* species are able to form resistant endospores, which help them survive harsh environmental and industrial processing conditions (Stein *et al.*, 2005; Abriouel *et al.*, 2010).

A key component of these biopreservation approaches is the use of bacteriocins, which are ribosomally synthesized antimicrobial peptides. These compounds usually show a relatively narrow spectrum of activity and inhibit closely related bacteria or specific foodborne pathogens by disrupting the integrity of their cell membranes (Zacharof *et al.*, 2012; Pato *et al.*, 2022). One major advantage of bacteriocins in food applications is that they are protein in nature and can be broken down by proteolytic enzymes in the human gastrointestinal tract, thereby preventing the accumulation of toxic residues. While LAB-derived bacteriocins such as nisin are well studied, *Bacillus* species are known to produce diverse bacteriocin-like inhibitory substances (BLIS) that demonstrate greater thermal and pH stability. Such stability is particularly important for their use in complex food systems (Abriouel *et al.*, 2011).

Although many studies have confirmed the antimicrobial activity of bacteriocins under laboratory (in vitro) conditions, there is still limited information regarding their systematic use in extending the shelf life of complex, heat-desiccated dairy products like barfi. Most available research has focused mainly on liquid milk, and the interaction between biopreservatives and the unique fat–protein–sugar matrix of traditional sweets remains insufficiently studied. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to develop and evaluate a bacteriocin-based biopreservative system specifically for milk and milk products. The objectives were to assess the antimicrobial effectiveness, characterize the active peptides, and examine their practical application in improving the shelf life of barfi under standard storage conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Standard microbial strains used in this study were procured from authenticated sources and maintained under appropriate laboratory conditions until further use. All microbiological media, agar, chemicals, and reagents were obtained from laboratory stock and prepared according to standard protocols. Fresh milk samples were purchased from a local dairy outlet, and barfi samples were obtained from a nearby sweet (mithai) shop under hygienic conditions. Milk samples were stored in sterile glass containers throughout the experimental period to minimize contamination.

Bacterial Strains and Culture Conditions

The probiotic strains used in this study included *Bacillus coagulans* GBI-30, *Bacillus clausii* UBBC-07, and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (ATCC 53103). All cultures were revived aseptically prior to experimental use. *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (ATCC 53103) was cultured in de Man, Rogosa and Sharpe (MRS) broth and incubated anaerobically at room temperature for 24 h. *Bacillus clausii* UBBC-07 was grown in Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth and incubated at room temperature for 24 h under shaking conditions. *Bacillus coagulans* GBI-30 was cultivated in Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose (YPD) broth and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Following incubation, cultures were subcultured periodically and maintained at 4 °C for short-term storage (Sarika *et al.*, 2010; Xu *et al.*, 2023; Kharwar *et al.*, 2022).

Isolation and Purification

Isolation of pure cultures was performed using the quadrant streaking technique. A loopful of each revived culture was streaked on its respective agar medium: MRS agar for *L. rhamnosus* GG (Sarika *et al.*, 2010), BHI agar for *B. clausii*, and YPD agar for *B. coagulans* (Kharwar *et al.*, 2022; Xu *et al.*, 2023). Plates were incubated at appropriate temperatures for 24-48 h. Well-isolated colonies were selected and repeatedly streaked until uniform colony morphology was obtained. Pure cultures were stored on agar slants at 4 °C for short-term use and preserved at -80 °C in glycerol-containing medium for long-term storage (Ahmadi *et al.*, 2025).

Cultural and Morphological Characterization

Colony characteristics including size, shape, elevation, margin, and pigmentation were recorded. Gram staining was performed to determine Gram reaction and cell morphology following standard procedures (Ahmadi *et al.*, 2025).

Catalase Test

Catalase activity was determined by placing a small portion of a bacterial colony on a clean glass slide and adding a drop of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Immediate bubble formation was recorded as a positive reaction (Ahmadi *et al.*, 2025).

Antimicrobial Activity Assay

Antimicrobial activity was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Escherichia coli*. After incubation, cultures were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C to obtain cell-free supernatants (CFS). Indicator pathogens were adjusted to OD 0.1 and seeded into molten nutrient agar. Wells (8 mm diameter) were prepared and filled with 100 µL CFS. Plates were pre-incubated at 4 °C for 2 h to allow diffusion and then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters. A clear zone ≥ 1 mm was considered positive for antimicrobial activity (Mulaw *et al.*, 2019).

Extraction and Partial Purification of Bacteriocin

Bacteriocin was extracted using ethyl acetate as described by Hassan *et al.* (2020) with minor modifications. Equal volumes of culture supernatant and ethyl acetate were mixed and allowed to separate. The organic phase was collected, pooled, and filtered through a 0.20 µm membrane filter. The partially purified bacteriocin was stored at 4 °C until further use.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

MIC was determined by the broth dilution method against selected test organisms. Two-fold serial dilutions were prepared, inoculated with standardized bacterial cultures, and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The lowest concentration showing no visible turbidity was recorded as MIC (Modified from Hassan *et al.*, 2011).

Protein Estimation

Protein concentration was estimated using the Folin–Lowry method (Lowry *et al.*, 1951). Absorbance was measured at 660 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) served as the standard.

Characterization of Bacteriocin

- **Temperature Stability** - Bacteriocin samples were exposed to different temperatures (37 °C, 47°C, 55°C, 75°C and 121 °C) for 10 min. Residual antimicrobial activity was assessed using the agar well diffusion method (Modified from Pato *et al.*, 2021).
- **pH Stability** - Samples were adjusted to pH 3, 5, 7, and 9 and incubated at 37 °C for 30 min. Antimicrobial activity was evaluated by agar well diffusion (Modified from Pato *et al.*, 2021).
- **Proteolytic Enzyme Sensitivity** - Pepsin (0.5% w/v) was used to evaluate the proteinaceous nature of bacteriocin. Residual activity was determined by agar well diffusion (Modified from Pato *et al.*, 2021).
- **Storage Stability** - Bacteriocin was stored at room temperature and 4 °C. Antimicrobial activity was assessed weekly upto four weeks (Modified from Mojgani *et al.*, 2009).

Preparation of Film-Forming Solution For Barfi Coating

The formulation was adapted from (Mei *et al.*, 2015) with modifications.

Chitosan (1.3%) was dissolved in 2% (v/v) acetic acid and stirred at 25 °C for 24 h. Separately, starch (5%) was gelatinized in distilled water at 75 °C for 60 min and cooled to ≤40 °C. Both solutions were mixed in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio.

Sorbitol (40%) was incorporated as a plasticizer due to improved mechanical properties compared to glycerol (Bezerra *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2023; Rahmatullah *et al.*, 2023). Citric acid (0.5%) was added as a cross-linking agent to enhance structural stability (Skov *et al.*, 2025; Sari *et al.*, 2025). The mixture was stirred for 60 min to ensure homogeneity. Partially purified bacteriocin was incorporated at its Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) level.

Film Casting And Coating Application

One portion was poured into sterile Petri plates and dried under controlled laboratory conditions to obtain uniform films for physicochemical characterization, including moisture content, swelling index, and water solubility (Contessa *et al.*, 2021).

Fresh barfi samples were pre-chilled at 4 °C and dip-coated in the film-forming solution for 10–30 s. The dipping process was repeated twice to ensure uniform coverage. Coated samples were dried at ≤ 40 °C until complete film formation (modified from Mei *et al.*, 2015).

- **Film Characterization** - Moisture content, swelling index, and water solubility were determined using gravimetric methods (Contessa *et al.*, 2021). All measurements were performed in triplicate and expressed as mean values. Moisture content, swelling percentage, and solubility were calculated using standard equations based on initial and final dry weights according to the method given by Contessa *et al.*, 2021.

Microbial Analysis of Barfi

Total viable count (TVC) was determined using the Miles and Misra drop plate technique. Yeast and mold counts were also performed. Samples (1 g) were serially diluted in sterile saline and plated on nutrient agar (TVC) and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (yeast/mold). Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 h (TVC) and 25 °C for 5 days (yeast/mold). Results were expressed as \log_{10} CFU/g (Modified from Amenu *et al.*, 2024; Hassan *et al.*, 2019; Hussain *et al.*, 2012).

Sensory Evaluation of Barfi

Sensory quality of coated and control barfi samples was evaluated based on odor and appearance during storage. Evaluation was performed under uniform lighting conditions using a 5-point scoring scale adapted from (Amenu *et al.*, 2024; Li *et al.*, 2023).

- **Odor Evaluation** - Approximately 10 g of sample was placed in a clean Petri plate and covered for 1–2 min to allow accumulation of volatile compounds. The cover was removed and odor was assessed using a single short sniff to avoid sensory fatigue. Odor was scored using a 5-point scale as follows

5 – Fresh, pleasant sweet milky aroma

4 – Slight change in aroma but acceptable

3 – Noticeable deviation from fresh odor (borderline acceptability)

2 – Unpleasant odor, unacceptable

1 – Highly offensive odor (sample discarded)

- **Appearance Evaluation** - Color and surface characteristics were visually examined by placing approximately 10 g of sample on a clean white surface and comparing with freshly

prepared control barfi. Changes such as surface dryness, minor cracks, or visible spoilage were recorded. Appearance was scored using the following 5-point scale:

- 5 – Fresh appearance, uniform color, smooth surface
- 4 – Slight change in color or minor surface dryness
- 3 – Noticeable change in color or slight surface cracks
- 2 – Visible spoilage signs (surface hardening or mold growth)
- 1 – Severe spoilage (extensive mold growth or structural breakdown)

Evaluation of Partially Purified Bacteriocin as a Biopreservative in Milk

The preservative potential of partially purified bacteriocin was evaluated in raw and pasteurized milk. Bacteriocin was added at 12.5% (prepared in distilled water) and mixed thoroughly. Untreated milk served as control. Samples were stored at room temperature (analyzed at 0, 4, 8, and 24 h) and at 4 °C (monitored daily for 6–7 days or until spoilage). Shelf life was assessed using microbiological, physicochemical, and sensory parameters following the approach of (Hameed *et al.*, 2019) with modifications.

Microbiological Analysis

Total viable count (TVC) was determined by the Miles and Misra drop plate method. Serially diluted samples were plated on nutrient agar, incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 h, and expressed as \log_{10} CFU/mL (Modified from Amenu *et al.*, 2024). Coliforms were enumerated on Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar after incubation at 35 °C for 24 h. Characteristic colonies were recorded and expressed as \log_{10} CFU/mL (Modified from Aliyo *et al.*, 2022; Hussain *et al.*, 2012).

Microbial activity was further assessed using the Methylene Blue Reduction Test (MBRT). Milk samples were incubated with methylene blue at 37 °C, and reduction time was recorded. Quality classification followed the criteria described by (Anwer *et al.*, 2018).

Physicochemical Analysis

pH was monitored during storage using a calibrated digital pH meter (Amenu *et al.*, 2024). Total titratable acidity (TTA) was determined by titration with 0.1 mol/L NaOH using phenolphthalein indicator and expressed as percentage lactic acid (Amenu *et al.*, 2024).

Sensory Evaluation

Spoilage was evaluated by clot-on-boiling test, odor assessment, and visual examination of color and appearance. Sensory analysis was performed by a panel of 10 evaluators using a 5-

point hedonic scale as described by (Amenu *et al.*, 2024; Li *et al.*, 2023), with slight modifications.

Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted in replicates. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Two-way ANOVA was performed using Microsoft Excel. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Preliminary Characterization of Probiotic Cultures

Pure cultures of *Bacillus clausii* UBBC-07, *Bacillus coagulans* GBI-30, and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (ATCC 53103) were obtained after repeated streaking on selective media. The morphological, microscopic, and biochemical characteristics of the isolates are summarized in Table 1. All isolates were Gram-positive rods. Catalase activity differentiated the strains, with both *Bacillus* isolates showing positive reactions, while *L. rhamnosus* GG was catalase negative. The observed characteristics were consistent with the known profiles of the respective probiotic strains, confirming culture purity prior to further experimentation.

Table 1: Morphological, Microscopic and Biochemical Characteristics of Probiotic Cultures.

Parameters	<i>Bacillus clausii</i> UBBC-07	<i>Bacillus coagulans</i> GBI-30	<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i> GG
Colony Size	Large	Large	Small
Colony Shape	Circular	Circular	Circular
Colony Color	Cream White	Off White	Whitish
Margin	Irregular	Entire	Entire
Opacity	Opaque	Opaque	Slightly Opaque
Consistency	Smooth	Smooth, shiny	Smooth, glistening
Elevation	Slightly Raised	Elevated	Convex
Gram Nature	Gram positive	Gram positive	Gram positive
Cell Morphology	Rod Shaped (Bacilli)	Rod Shaped (Bacilli)	Rod shaped
Catalase Test	Positive	Positive	Negative

Antimicrobial Activity of Crude Bacteriocin

The antimicrobial activity of crude bacteriocin preparations from *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (ATCC 53103), *Bacillus clausii* UBBC-07, and *Bacillus coagulans* GBI-30 was evaluated using the agar well diffusion assay (Table 2). Crude bacteriocin from *L. rhamnosus* GG inhibited all tested organisms, showing the broadest spectrum of activity. The preparation

from *B. coagulans* GBI-30 exhibited limited inhibition against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Bacillus cereus*, whereas no activity was observed against *Staphylococcus aureus* or *Escherichia coli*. No detectable inhibition was recorded for *B. clausii* UBBC-07 under the experimental conditions.

Table 2: Antimicrobial activity of crude bacteriocin produced by probiotic strains against selected test organisms.

Probiotic Strain	Zone of inhibition (mm) against test organisms			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i> GG	14.33 ± 1.5	18.33 ± 0.5	18.66 ± 2.3	16 ± 0
<i>Bacillus clausii</i> UBBC-07	-	-	-	-
<i>Bacillus coagulans</i> GBI-30	-	-	12.33 ± 0.5	11.33 ± 0.5

Antimicrobial Activity of Partially Purified Bacteriocin

Following ethyl acetate extraction, antimicrobial activity was reassessed (Fig. 1). The extract from *L. rhamnosus* GG retained inhibitory activity against all test organisms, with zones exceeding those of the solvent control. In contrast, inhibition observed for *B. clausii* UBBC-07 and *B. coagulans* GBI-30 was comparable to the ethyl acetate control, and no activity against *S. aureus* was detected. These results indicate that only the partially purified preparation from *L. rhamnosus* GG demonstrated antimicrobial activity beyond solvent-associated effects.

Fig. 1: Antimicrobial activity of partially purified bacteriocin.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

MIC values of the partially purified bacteriocin preparations are presented in Table 3. The extract from *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (ATCC 53103) exhibited the lowest MIC values against all tested organisms, indicating greater antimicrobial potency. In contrast, extracts from *Bacillus clausii* UBBC-07 and *Bacillus coagulans* GBI-30 showed inhibitory effects only at higher concentrations. Based on these findings, *L. rhamnosus* GG was selected for further characterization and application studies.

Table 3: MIC of partially purified bacteriocin against test organisms.

Probiotic strains	MIC of partially purified bacteriocin (mg%)			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i> GG	15.9519	7.9760	7.9760	15.9519
<i>Bacillus clausii</i> UBBC-07	33.92	33.92	33.92	33.92
<i>Bacillus coagulans</i> GBI-30	27.04	27.04	27.04	54.09

Protein Estimation

The protein concentration of the partially purified bacteriocin was determined using the Folin–Lowry method with bovine serum albumin (BSA) as the standard. The calibration curve showed good linearity ($R^2 = 0.9855$) (Fig. 2). Based on interpolation from the regression equation, the protein concentration of the partially purified bacteriocin was calculated as 1.276 mg/mL after applying the dilution factor.

Table 4: Protein Concentration Of Partially Purified Bacteriocin.

Sample	OD (Rep 1)	OD (Rep 2)	Mean OD	Conc. (µg/mL) Diluted	Dilution Factor	Final Conc. (µg/mL)	% Protein
Partially Purified Bacteriocin	1.7	1.8	1.75	127.615	10	1276.15	0.128

Fig. 2: Standard curve of BSA used for protein estimation of partially purified bacteriocin. Absorbance values of known BSA concentrations were plotted to generate a calibration curve, and the concentration of bacteriocin was calculated by interpolation from the regression line.

Characterization of Partially Purified Bacteriocin

- **Effect of Temperature** - The effect of temperature on antimicrobial activity is presented in Table 5. The bacteriocin retained activity at 37 °C but showed complete loss of inhibition following exposure to higher temperatures (≥ 47 °C). The untreated control maintained activity, indicating thermal inactivation at elevated temperatures.

Table 5: Effect of temperature on antimicrobial activity of partially purified bacteriocin.

Temperature	Zone of inhibition (mm) against test organisms			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
37°C	10.33 ± 0.5	11.66 ± 0.5	10.33 ± 0.5	11.0 ± 0.0
Control (Bacteriocin without treatment)	10.0 ± 0.0	11.33 ± 1.15	12.0 ± 0.0	11.0 ± 0.0

No inhibition observed at 47°C, 55°C, 75°C and 121°C.

- **Effect of pH** - pH stability results are shown in Table 6. Antimicrobial activity was retained at pH 5 and pH 7, with greater activity near neutral pH. No inhibition was detected under strongly acidic (pH 3) or alkaline conditions (pH 9 and 11), indicating sensitivity to extreme pH levels.

Table 6. Effect of pH on antimicrobial activity of partially purified bacteriocin.

pH	Zone of inhibition (mm) against test organisms			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
5	10.33 ± 0.5	14.33 ± 0.5	12.33 ± 0.5	11.33 ± 1.15
7	10.66 ± 1.15	13.33 ± 0.5	12.0 ± 0.0	10.0 ± 0.0
Control (Bacteriocin without treatment)	10.0 ± 0.0	12.33 ± 2.3	12.0 ± 0.0	11.0 ± 0.0

No inhibition observed at pH 3, 9 and 11.

- **Effect of Proteolytic Enzyme (Pepsin)** - As shown in Table 7, pepsin treatment resulted in complete loss of antimicrobial activity, whereas the untreated control retained inhibitory effects. This confirms the proteinaceous nature of the active compound.

Table 7: Effect of pepsin treatment on the antimicrobial activity of partially purified bacteriocin.

Treatment	Zone of inhibition (mm) against test organisms			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
Partially Purified Bacteriocin (Pepsin-treated)	-	-	-	-
Control (Untreated bacteriocin)	10.0 ± 0.0	12.33 ± 2.3	10.66 ± 0.5	10.0 ± 0.0

- **Stability During Storage** - Storage stability data are presented in table 8 and 9. A gradual decline in antimicrobial activity was observed over four weeks at both room temperature and 4 °C. However, measurable inhibition was retained throughout the storage period under both conditions, indicating moderate stability of the bacteriocin.

Table 8: Stability of bacteriocin during storage at room temperature (RT).

Week	Zone of inhibition (mm) against test organisms			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
Week 0	14.33 ± 1.5	18.33 ± 0.5	18.66 ± 2.3	16 ± 0
Week 1	13.7 ± 0.6	16.7 ± 1.2	14.7 ± 0.6	14.7 ± 1.2
Week 2	13.3 ± 0.6	16.7 ± 0.6	14.3 ± 0.6	15.7 ± 0.6
Week 3	12.7 ± 0.6	16.7 ± 1.2	13.7 ± 0.6	15.3 ± 1.2
Week 4	12.7 ± 0.6	14.3 ± 0.6	13.0 ± 0.0	13.3 ± 0.6

Table 9. Stability of bacteriocin during storage at 4°C.

Week	Zone of inhibition (mm) against test organisms			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
Week 0	14.33 ± 1.5	18.33 ± 0.5	18.66 ± 2.3	16 ± 0
Week 1	13.7 ± 0.6	17.0 ± 0.0	14.3 ± 1.2	14.7 ± 1.2
Week 2	13.0 ± 0.0	14.7 ± 1.2	14.3 ± 0.6	15.7 ± 0.6
Week 3	12.3 ± 0.6	12.3 ± 1.2	12.7 ± 0.6	12.3 ± 0.6
Week 4	12.7 ± 0.6	12.0 ± 0.0	12.0 ± 0.0	12.3 ± 0.6

Fig. 3. Stability of partially purified bacteriocin during storage at RT (left) and 4°C (right).

The graph illustrates the residual antimicrobial activity of partially purified bacteriocin during storage at RT and 4°C over 4 weeks of storage intervals. Antimicrobial activity was assessed at regular intervals and expressed as mean values. Error bars represent the standard deviation of triplicate determinations, indicating the reproducibility of the experiment.

Characterization of Developed Bioactive Edible Film

The developed bioactive film showed $25.0 \pm 0.0\%$ moisture content, $100.0 \pm 0.0\%$ swelling index, and $70.0 \pm 8.66\%$ water solubility (Table 10). Visual observation indicated that the films were uniform, transparent, and flexible, with no visible cracks after drying (Fig. 4). Incorporation of bacteriocin did not adversely affect film integrity or handling properties.

Table 10: Physical properties of developed bioactive film.

Parameters	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	Mean ± SD
Moisture content (%)	25	25	25	25.0 ± 0.0
Swelling index (%)	100	100	100	100.0 ± 0.0
Water solubility (%)	75	60	75	70.0 ± 8.66

Fig. 4. Morphological and physical appearance of the developed bioactive films. (Left) Comparative visual observation of films without bacteriocin and with bacteriocin incorporation after drying; (Right) transparency, uniformity, and flexibility of the optimized film during manual handling.

Effect of Bacteriocin-Incorporated Edible Coating on Shelf Life of Barfi

Microbial Analysis

Changes in total viable count (TVC) and yeast and mold count (YMC) during storage are presented in Figs. 5. Microbial load increased progressively in all samples over time. The control barfi exhibited rapid microbial growth and became unacceptable by day 8. The coated sample without bacteriocin showed a comparatively slower increase but reached spoilage by day 10. In contrast, the bacteriocin-incorporated coated barfi demonstrated delayed microbial growth and remained acceptable up to day 10, with spoilage observed on day 11.

Two-way ANOVA revealed that both storage time and treatment had a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on TVC and YMC, indicating that incorporation of bacteriocin significantly influenced microbial stability during storage. Visual changes observed during storage (Fig. 6) were consistent with microbial findings.

Fig. 5: Changes in Total Viable Count (Left) and Yeast Mold Count (Right) (log₁₀ CFU/g) of control and coated barfi samples during storage.

Fig. 6: Visual appearance of control and coated barfi samples during storage showing progression of spoilage. Control barfi spoiled on day 8, coated barfi without bacteriocin on day 10, and bacteriocin-coated barfi on day 11.

Sensory Evaluation

Sensory scores for odor and appearance are presented in Table 11. All samples were rated excellent during the initial storage period. A gradual decline in sensory quality was observed over time; however, the reduction was more pronounced in the control sample.

Table 11: Sensory evaluation scores of barfi samples during storage (5-point hedonic scale).

Days	Control Barfi		Coated Barfi Without Bacteriocin		Coated Barfi With Bacteriocin	
	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance
0	5	5	5	5	5	5
1	5	5	5	5	5	5
2	5	5	5	5	5	5
3	5	5	5	5	5	5
5	4	4	5	5	5	5
8	1	1	4	4	4	4
10	Not Evaluated	Not Evaluated	1	1	3	3
11	*Not Evaluated	*Not Evaluated	*Not Evaluated	*Not Evaluated	1	1

5 = Excellent, 4 = Good, 3 = Acceptable, 2 = Poor, 1 = Spoiled/Unacceptable

*Not evaluated after spoilage of the respective sample.

Evaluation of Partially Purified Bacteriocin as a Biopreservative in Milk

Microbial Parameters

- Storage at Room Temperature** - Changes in microbial parameters (TVC, Coliform count) of raw and pasteurized milk stored at room temperature are presented in Fig. 7. At room temperature, microbial counts increased rapidly in both raw and pasteurized milk. Untreated raw milk showed accelerated spoilage and was not evaluated beyond 8 h. Pasteurized control samples also exhibited rapid microbial proliferation under ambient conditions. In contrast, bacteriocin-treated samples demonstrated comparatively lower total viable counts and coliform counts at corresponding intervals, indicating a delay in microbial growth. Two-way ANOVA confirmed that both storage time and treatment had a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on microbial parameters.

- Storage at 4 °C** - Results of refrigerated storage for microbial parameters (TVC, Coliform count) are shown in Fig. 8. Refrigeration significantly slowed microbial growth in both raw and pasteurized milk; however, progressive increases in total viable count and coliform count were observed during storage. Bacteriocin-treated samples consistently showed lower microbial counts than untreated controls. Statistical analysis indicated significant effects ($p < 0.05$) of both storage time and treatment on microbial load.

Fig. 7. Changes in total viable count (TVC) and coliform count of raw and pasteurized milk during storage at room temperature.

(Left) graph showing changes in TVC during storage. The counts are in Log₁₀ CFU/mL.

(Right) graph showing changes in coliform count during storage. The counts are in Log₁₀ CFU/mL.

Fig. 8. Changes in total viable count (TVC) and coliform count of raw and pasteurized milk during storage at refrigerated temperature.

(Left) graph showing changes in TVC during storage. The counts are in Log₁₀ CFU/mL.

(Right) graph showing changes in coliform count during storage. The counts are in Log₁₀ CFU/mL.

Methyl Red Reduction Test (MBRT)

- **Storage at Room Temperature** - MBRT reduction time decreased progressively during storage in all samples, reflecting increasing microbial activity. However, bacteriocin-treated milk consistently showed longer reduction times compared to controls. The results are given in table 12.
- **Storage at 4 °C** - In pasteurized milk, MBRT reduction time gradually decreased over storage, with treated samples retaining dye for longer durations compared to controls. The results are presented in table 13.

Table 12: Methylene Blue Reduction Test (MBRT) Quality Grading of Raw and Pasteurized Milk at Room Temperature.

Storage Time (Hours)	Raw Milk		Pasteurized Milk	
	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin
0	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
4	Fair	Fair	Fair	Fair
8	Poor	Fair	Poor	Fair
24	-	Poor	-	Poor

Table 13: Methylene Blue Reduction Test (MBRT) Quality Grading of Pasteurized Milk at Refrigerated Temperature.

Storage Time (Days)	Pasteurized Milk	
	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin
0	Excellent	Excellent
1	Excellent	Excellent
3	Good	Excellent
4	Fair	Good
5	Fair	Fair
6	-	Poor

Class I (Excellent): No decolorization observed within 8 hours

Class II (Good): Decolorization occurring between 6 to 8 hours

Class III (Fair): Decolorization occurring between 2 to 6 hours

Class IV (Poor): Decolorization occurring within 2 hours

Physicochemical Analysis

- **Storage at Room Temperature** - Titratable acidity increased and pH decreased during storage, with more pronounced changes in untreated samples. Treated milk exhibited a

comparatively slower rise in acidity and a more gradual decline in pH. Results of titratable acidity are presented in fig. 8 and results of pH are presented in table 14.

- **Storage at 4 °C** - Titratable acidity increased steadily in all samples, whereas the rate of increase was lower in bacteriocin-treated milk. Similarly, pH declined during storage, with treated samples maintaining comparatively higher pH values. Results of titratable acidity are presented in fig. 9 and results of pH are presented in table 15.

Fig. 8: Variation in titratable acidity of raw and pasteurized milk during storage at room temperature (left) and at 4°C (right). Error bars represent the mean \pm standard deviation of duplicate observations.

Table 14: pH of Raw and Pasteurized Milk During Storage at Room Temperature.

Storage Time (Hours)	pH Of Raw Milk		pH Of Pasteurized Milk	
	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin
0	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.6
4	5.6	6.1	6.1	6.3
8	4.2	5.2	5.4	5.9
24	-	3.9	-	4.1

Table 15: pH of Raw and Pasteurized Milk During Storage at Refrigerated Temperature.

Storage Time (Days)	pH Of Raw Milk		pH Of Pasteurized Milk	
	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin	Without Bacteriocin	With Bacteriocin
0	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.6
1	6.1	6.5	6.6	6.6
3	5.6	6.1	6.4	6.5
4	4.9	5.5	6.1	6.3
5	-	4.8	5.2	5.9
6	-	-	-	4.9

Clot on boiling test - Clot-on-boiling tests supported these findings, untreated milk showed coagulation earlier during storage, whereas bacteriocin-treated samples remained stable for a longer period. The visual representation of both pasteurized and raw milk stored at refrigerated temperature are presented in fig. 10, (A- raw milk) and (B - pasteurized milk).

Fig. 10: Clot on boiling test of raw and pasteurized milk stored at 4°C. (A) Day 0 samples (untreated and bacteriocin-treated) showed no clot formation. By day 4, coagulation was observed in untreated milk, while treated samples remained stable. (B) Untreated milk exhibited clotting after boiling, whereas bacteriocin-treated milk showed no coagulation, indicating improved storage stability.

Sensory Analysis

Sensory scores for odor and appearance are presented in Table 16 (room temperature) and Table 17 (4 °C). Sensory quality declined progressively during storage under both conditions, with faster deterioration observed at room temperature. In both raw and pasteurized milk, bacteriocin-treated samples retained acceptable sensory scores for a longer duration compared to untreated controls. Refrigerated storage further extended overall acceptability.

Table 16: Sensory Evaluation of Milk at Room Temperature (n = 10).

Storage Time (Hours)	Sensory Evaluation Of Raw Milk				Sensory Evaluation Of Pasteurized Milk			
	Without Bacteriocin		With Bacteriocin		Without Bacteriocin		With Bacteriocin	
	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance
0	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
8	1	1	3	4	1	1	3	4
24	NE	NE	1	1	NE	NE	1	1

Table 17: Sensory Evaluation of Milk at 4°C (n = 10)

Storage Time (Hours)	Sensory Evaluation Of Raw Milk				Sensory Evaluation Of Pasteurized Milk			
	Without Bacteriocin		With Bacteriocin		Without Bacteriocin		With Bacteriocin	
	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance	Odor	Appearance
0	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
3	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5
4	1	1	3	4	3	4	4	5
5	NE	NE	1	1	1	1	3	4
6	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	1	2

5 = Excellent, 4 = Good, 3 = Acceptable, 2 = Poor, 1 = Spoiled/Unacceptable NE = Not Evaluated

The application of bacteriocin effectively retarded microbial growth in milk under both ambient and refrigerated storage conditions. The treated samples demonstrated a slower increase in log₁₀ CFU/mL compared to controls, thereby extending the microbiological stability and delaying spoilage onset.

DISCUSSION

The current study evaluated the efficacy of a partially purified bacteriocin from *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* as a natural biopreservative in milk and barfi. The results demonstrate that bacteriocin treatment effectively controlled microbial proliferation, delayed acid development, and maintained sensory quality in both products. The preservative effect was more pronounced under refrigeration, indicating that while the bacteriocin remains active across temperatures, its effectiveness is enhanced at lower storage conditions. These findings support the growing interest in natural alternatives to synthetic preservatives in dairy systems. The identity of the standard bacterial strains was confirmed through morphological and biochemical characterization prior to antimicrobial assays. The observed Gram reaction and catalase activity corresponded with established characteristics of the respective organisms. Such confirmation is essential, as bacteriocin activity depends largely on the structural and physiological properties of the target cells. During preliminary screening, a clear difference in antimicrobial activity was observed between *L. rhamnosus* and the tested *Bacillus* strains. The crude extract of *L. rhamnosus* produced distinct inhibition zones, whereas *Bacillus clausii* and *Bacillus coagulans* showed negligible activity. Similar findings have been reported earlier, where probiotic *Bacillus* strains exhibited limited antagonism in diffusion-based assays (Khatri et al., 2019). This may reflect strain-specific metabolite production or

limitations of agar diffusion methods for detecting antimicrobial peptides from spore-forming bacteria. In contrast, the bacteriocin from *L. rhamnosus* demonstrated broad-spectrum activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms, consistent with the report of Sarika *et al.* (2010), who documented strong inhibition of pathogens including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*.

Partial purification using ethyl acetate significantly enhanced antimicrobial activity. The solvent extraction likely concentrated the active peptide while removing interfering substances. Similar recovery of *Lactobacillus* bacteriocins in ethyl acetate fractions has been reported by Hassan *et al.* (2020), particularly where ammonium sulphate precipitation was ineffective. Although further purification would be necessary for complete characterization, the present findings confirm the suitability of solvent extraction as a preliminary step. The microtiter plate assay demonstrated a clear concentration-dependent inhibitory effect, with MIC values indicating substantial potency at low concentrations. Comparable strain-specific variability in susceptibility has been described by Hassan *et al.* (2011), emphasizing that bacteriocin efficacy depends on target cell characteristics. Protein estimation supported the proteinaceous nature of the antimicrobial compound, showing consistency between protein concentration and inhibitory activity, in agreement with Trupti *et al.* (2024). Stability studies revealed that the bacteriocin retained activity across a moderate range of pH and temperature, though extreme conditions caused partial loss. While broader stability has been reported by Patel *et al.* (2021), differences may relate to purification level or strain specificity. The present observations align with those of Mojgani *et al.* (2009), who reported similar stability patterns in *Lactobacillus* bacteriocins.

Application of the bacteriocin within a starch–chitosan coating on barfi significantly improved shelf stability, reducing microbial load and delaying yeast and mold growth. The coating functioned both as a physical barrier and as a carrier of antimicrobial activity. Comparable preservation mechanisms have been described in chitosan–starch coatings for cheese, where incorporation of antimicrobial agents effectively limited spoilage during refrigerated storage (Mei *et al.*, 2014).

In milk, bacteriocin treatment consistently reduced total viable counts and suppressed coliform growth. Similar shelf-life extension effects of bacteriocins such as nisin have been reported by Zeinab *et al.* (2018). The reduction in coliforms is particularly important, as these organisms are indicators of hygienic quality and spoilage in milk (Aliyo and Teklemariam,

2022). Treated samples also showed a slower increase in titratable acidity and a more stable pH profile, indicating reduced fermentative activity, consistent with findings by Amenu and Bacha (2024). The Methylene Blue Reduction Test further supported these observations, as treated milk maintained longer reduction times, reflecting lower microbial activity (Anwer *et al.*, 2018).

Overall, the consistent trends across microbiological, physicochemical, and sensory parameters demonstrate that partially purified bacteriocin from *L. rhamnosus* effectively delayed spoilage in milk and barfi. These findings highlight its potential application as a natural preservative in dairy products, although further validation under large-scale storage conditions is warranted.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that the bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* is a highly effective natural alternative to synthetic preservatives in dairy systems. The partially purified extract exhibited robust antimicrobial potency and functional stability across practical pH and temperature ranges, confirming its suitability for food-grade applications. When applied to milk and barfi - either through direct incorporation or as part of a biopolymer coating - the bacteriocin significantly suppressed microbial proliferation and delayed physicochemical spoilage, effectively extending the shelf life of these products. These findings validate the systematic preservation effect of *L. rhamnosus* bacteriocin and establish a strong foundation for its commercial use. Future research should focus on refining the purification process through advanced chromatography and utilizing lyophilization to improve formulation stability and dosing accuracy. Additionally, exploring the synergy between this bacteriocin and other hurdle technologies will be essential for optimizing its performance and ensuring safety across diverse industrial food matrices.

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